

CAUSATION

International Journal of Science

Beyond LDL: Reevaluating the Pathogenesis of Atherosclerosis

Short communication

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Impressum:

CAUSATION

International Journal Of Science

Chief-Editor / V. i. S. d. P.:

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DE-26409 Wittmund-Ardorf (Germany)

© Editorial Team: **EDITORIAL TEAM**

🌐 Website: WWW.CAUSATION.EU

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☎ Phone: +(49) 4466 - 333

Year: 2025; Volume: 20; Issue: 10; pp. 5–30.

✉ Received: October 13, 2024

✓ Accepted: October 13, 2024

📅 Published: October 13, 2024

📖 [Deutsche Nationalbibliothek Frankfurt](#)

📄 [ISSN: 1863-9542](#)

[DOI:10.5281/zenodo.13926273](#)

🔍 Find in: [Zenodo Orcid Academia ...](#)

Abstract**BACKGROUND:**

Atherosclerosis is a major contributor to cardiovascular disease, traditionally linked to elevated levels of low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol. However, recent findings raise critical questions regarding the causal relationship between LDL and the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This study re-analysed data from approximately 14,000 patients, focusing on the relationship between LDL lowering and related deaths. We employed new statistical methods to assess the relationship between LDL levels and outcomes.

RESULTS:

Our findings revealed a lack of a definitive causal link between LDL levels and the incidence of atherosclerosis. While a reduction in LDL cholesterol was achieved in the patient cohort, this did not cause a significant decrease in all-cause mortality, suggesting that other factors than LDL may play a more critical role in the development of atherosclerosis.

CONCLUSION:

The results of this study cast doubt on the established paradigm of LDL as the primary driver of atherosclerosis. This reevaluation invites further investigation into alternative mechanisms underlying atherosclerosis and highlights the necessity for a more nuanced approach to cardiovascular risk assessment and management.

Keywords:

LDL; Death; Atherosclerosis; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

© Reviewer 1: None/Author.

© Reviewer 2: None.

© Reviewer 3: None.

1. Introduction

Atherosclerosis (see [Guijarro and Cosín-Sales, 2021](#)) is a chronic and progressive disease characterized by the accumulation of lipids, inflammatory cells, and fibrous elements within arterial walls. This condition poses significant challenges not only to individuals affected by it but also to society at large due to its association with cardiovascular (see [Borén et al., 2020](#)) diseases (CVDs), which remain the leading cause of morbidity and mortality globally. The societal burden includes increased healthcare costs, reduced productivity, and diminished quality of life for affected individuals.

Multifaceted Risk Factors

The risk factors (see [Phrommintikul et al., 2017](#)) currently considered in relation to atherosclerosis are multifaceted and include metabolic, lifestyle, and genetic components. Among these, low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol is frequently regarded as a key target for intervention. High levels of LDL (see [Khan and Michos, 2020](#)) cholesterol are often linked to the development of atherosclerotic plaques, which can lead to cardiovascular events such as heart attacks and strokes.

LDL Reduction and Mortality

Statins, for example, have long been prescribed for LDL cholesterol reduction, yet their broader effects on cardiovascular health and mortality warrant further scrutiny.

In brief, a critical question arises, is the lowering of LDL cholesterol (see [Catapano et al., 2011](#)) itself decisive in mitigating cardiovascular risk, or is the reduction of LDL merely a side effect while the effectiveness of such interventions depend on the specific medications employed to achieve this reduction?

In instances where a successful reduction of LDL cholesterol is demonstrated, it is essential to provide robust evidence of a simultaneous decrease in all-cause mortality. The notion all-cause mortality includes all deaths, and thus far deaths from cardiovascular causes too. A reduction in all-cause mortality would provide additional support for the LDL hypothesis of atherosclerosis.

Conversely, demonstrating LDL reduction without a corresponding decrease in all-cause mortality would challenge the long-held belief in LDL's primary role in atherosclerosis and cardiovascular disease. Such a result would necessitate a critical examination of whether LDL is genuinely causally linked to the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis. However, assumed that a definitive causal relationship between LDL and atherosclerosis exists, we must then consider the pharmacological implications: Has the medication responsible for the LDL reduction inadvertently causally contributed to all-cause mortality?

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

Mechanism of Bempedoic Acid

Bempedoic acid is an oral medication that targets cholesterol synthesis and has become of interest for patients who are statin-intolerant—those who cannot tolerate statins due to muscle pain, liver enzyme elevation, or other adverse effects. Given that statins are typically the first-line treatment for reducing cardiovascular (CV) events in patients with high LDL cholesterol, alternative treatments like bempedoic acid can offer a promising solution for patients who struggle with statin intolerance. Bempedoic acid works by inhibiting the ATP citrate lyase (ACL) enzyme in the liver, which is involved in cholesterol biosynthesis. This mechanism is distinct from statins, which inhibit HMG-CoA reductase, another enzyme in the cholesterol synthesis pathway. Because bempedoic acid which is a prodrug that only becomes active in the liver and not in muscle tissue has a lower risk of muscle-related side effects, which is beneficial for patients intolerant to statins.

Evidence of Cardiovascular Outcomes: The CLEAR Outcomes Trial

The *CLEAR Outcomes* trial (see [Nissen et al., 2023](#)) which investigated the effects of bempedoic acid on cardiovascular events specifically in patients who were statin-intolerant was a multi-year trial with a median follow-up duration of 40.6 months (approximately 3.4 years). This study involved 13,970 patients randomized into two groups, one receiving bempedoic acid and the other a placebo. These participants were spread across multiple countries, though specific details of each location are not available in detail. However, clinical trials of this scale often cover regions in North America, Europe, and other continents to include diverse patient populations and ensure broad applicability of the results. The trial was a double-blind, placebo-controlled study involving about 14,000 participants with high cardiovascular risk who could not tolerate statins due to adverse effects.

		Death from any cause		
		YES	NO	
Bempedoic Acid	YES	434	6558	6992
	NO	420	6558	6978
		854	13116	13,970

Table 1. Bempedoic acid excludes cardiovascular death?

Bempedoic acid is able to reduce LDL cholesterol while the use of bempedoic acid is not intended to replace statins but rather to provide an effective alternative for patients who are unable to take statins due to side effects.

Mortality Rates and Causes

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) are the leading cause (see [Organization et al., 2012](#)) of mortality globally, accounting for approximately **30% of deaths worldwide annually** (see [Mathers, 2008](#)).

“Cardiovascular diseases are the leading cause of death in the world, particularly among women; such diseases caused almost 32% of all deaths in women and 27% in men in 2004.” (see [Mathers et al., 2009](#))

This high rate is believed to be largely due to lifestyle-related factors, including diet, physical inactivity, and widespread risk factors such as hypertension, diabetes, and smoking. Developed countries report higher CVD-related mortality, partly due to longer life expectancy and the prevalence of these risk factors. However, in *developing countries*, infectious diseases remain a significant cause of death. Limited healthcare access, low vaccination rates, and other socio-economic factors contribute to the higher infectious disease mortality in these regions. This disparity highlights the varying impact of lifestyle diseases and infectious diseases on global mortality rates.

Expected Mortality Reduction in Treatment Group

Assuming that primarily a reduction in LDL cholesterol leads to a reduction in cardiovascular mortality, the treatment group should have an approximately **30% lower mortality rate** compared to the placebo group.

In the placebo group, **420 out of 6978** patients died over the study period. In the treatment group, **6992 patients** were observed over the same period. If LDL reduction were an effective approach to reducing cardiovascular mortality, we would expect approximately **30% fewer deaths** in the treatment group, adjusted for the slightly larger number of patients, as follows:

$$(420 \times (1 - 0.30)) \times \frac{6992}{6978} = 294.18 \approx 294 \text{ expected deaths in the treatment group.}$$

Thus, the expected mortality in the treatment group would have to be about **294 patients** if LDL reduction leads directly to lower cardiovascular mortality. This is viewed by the next table.

		Death from any cause		
		YES	NO	
Bempedoic	YES	294	6698	6992
Acid	NO	420	6558	6978
		714	13256	13970

Table 2. Bempedoic acid excludes cardiovascular death?

The result obtained has been:

$$p(\text{Bempedoic acid} \mid \text{Death from any cause}) = \left(1 - \frac{434}{13970}\right) = 0.96893$$

Under conditions of a **two-sided hypothesis** we do expect at least:

$$p(\text{Bempedoic acid} \mid \text{Death from any cause}) = \left(1 - \frac{294}{13970}\right) = 0.97895$$

or higher. For a **one-sided hypothesis**, we expect:

$$p(\text{Bempedoic acid} \mid \text{Death from any cause}) = \left(1 - \frac{\left(\frac{294}{13970}\right)}{2}\right) = 0.98948$$

or higher.

2.2. Methods

Exclusion relationship (Conditio exclusionis)

In nature, it occurs that the occurrence of one event A_t at a specific time t or Bernoulli trial t makes the occurrence of another event B_t impossible. In other words, if $A_t = 1$ occurs at a specific time t , it means that event $B_t = 0$ does not occur, and vice versa. If $B_t = 1$ occurs at a specific time t , it means that event $A_t = 0$ does not occur. The relationship between such two events, whose occurrences exclude each other at a specific time or within a specific period, is known as “mutually exclusive events.” Even though we may not always know the specific scientific processes underlying such events in detail, we are still able to recognize such relationships. To approach this issue, let us consider a concrete, natural example. In the following, we define a living, male, human being as a man, which among other characteristics, possesses the following: alive, belonging to the species *Homo sapiens*, penis, testes, vas deferens, XY chromosomes, etc., and does not possess fallopian tubes, ovaries, a uterus, or a vagina, etc. We now ask the question: Is being male and being pregnant mutually compatible? In other words, can a man be pregnant? If yes, why? If not, why not? Is it possible to answer such a question with a certain degree of certainty. To investigate this issue, we conduct an examination and obtain the data detailed in Table 3.

Table 3. A_t excludes B_t and vice versa.

		Conditioned (Pregnant) B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition (Man) A_t	TRUE	+0	1	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	1	1	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

Let us take a closer look at the data we have collected:

1. **Man = false and Pregnant = true:** This case describes a woman who is pregnant. In other words, there are women who are pregnant. But are all women automatically pregnant? Of course not.
2. **Man = false and Pregnant = false:** This case describes a woman who is not pregnant. This means that not all women are automatically pregnant. It is also normal for women not to be pregnant when no pregnancy is present. So, women can be either pregnant or not. But what about men?
3. **Man = true and Pregnant = false:** This case shows that there are many men who are not pregnant. If we were to consider only this case, we might conclude that men cannot become pregnant, as we have observed many men who are not pregnant. This also appears to be a normal physiological state. To gain final clarity, we continue our investigation.
4. **Man = true and Pregnant = true:** Despite countless attempts and increasing the sample size, we could not observe a single instance where a man was pregnant. This case did not occur biologically in our study. In other words, a man cannot become pregnant. Being a man and being pregnant are mutually exclusive.

Example I.

Pregnancy is characterized by various properties and is subject to specific conditions. These conditions include biological, hormonal, and physiological factors, each of which must align for pregnancy to occur. One of the most fundamental conditions is the sex of the individual. Table 4 highlights the exclusion relationship from another perspective. The existence of one event (e.g., not being a man) precludes the occurrence of another event or state (e.g., being pregnant). An individual identified as not a man (when $A_t = \text{FALSE}$) may have the potential for pregnancy (c_t). However, even if an individual is not a man ($\underline{A}_t$), pregnancy may or may not occur, as represented by the variables c_t and d_t . The mutually exclusive relationship between being a man and the possibility of pregnancy is the natural foundation of the principle **without** being not a man, **no** pregnancy (see Table 4). Nonetheless, without the condition of not being a man, pregnancy cannot occur; hence, being a human but not a man is a necessary condition for pregnancy. Conversely, the statement **if** pregnancy, **then** not a man is equally valid at the same time t or in a Bernoulli trial at time t . Thus far, table 5 shifts our perspective by showing that if pregnancy is present ($B_t = \text{TRUE}$), then the individual cannot be a man ($a_t = 0$). This again reinforces the mutually exclusive relationship between the states of being a man and being pregnant. Thus, if pregnancy is absent in a human, the individual could either be a man (b_t) or not a man (d_t).

Table 4. Without not a man, no pregnancy

		Pregnancy		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Man	FALSE	c_t	d_t	$\underline{A}_t$
	TRUE	$a_t = 0$	b_t	A_t
		B_t	$\underline{B}_t$	+1

Table 5. If pregnancy then not a man

		Man		
		FALSE	TRUE	
Pregnancy	TRUE	c_t	$a_t = 0$	B_t
	FALSE	d_t	b_t	$\underline{B}_t$
		$\underline{A}_t$	A_t	+1

Indeed, a classic example of mutually exclusive events is the incompatibility of ‘man’ and ‘pregnant’. However, many other examples in nature illustrate similar circumstances. A simple case is the behavior of particles and antiparticles in quantum physics, which annihilate each other upon contact. In human medicine, antidotes play a crucial role and are another example of an exclusion relationship. Antidotes can counteract the effects of specific events, toxins or overdoses, allowing doctors to reverse potentially life-threatening events or situations. For example, naloxone is a well-known antidote used to treat opioid overdoses. It works by binding to the same receptors in the brain that opioids target, effectively blocking the harmful effects of the overdose. This rapid action can restore normal respiration in patients who have stopped breathing due to opioid toxicity. The availability of such antidotes is crucial in emergency medicine, as they can provide life-saving interventions within minutes. These observations lead to the general conclusion that certain natural events or states are mutually exclusive under specific conditions. This has profound implications for our understanding of nature and underscores the importance of analyzing these events in greater mathematical detail.

DEFINITION 1 (Exclusion relationship [EXCL]).

Mathematically, the exclusion relationship (EXCL), commonly denoted as $p(A_t | B_t)$ in statistics and probability theory, is rigorously defined in the literature (see also Barukčić, 2021) as ¹ follows: (see also Barukčić, 1989, pp. 68-70)

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t | B_t) &\equiv p(A_t \uparrow B_t) \\
 &\equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (\underline{A}_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{b + c + d}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{b + \underline{A}}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{c + \underline{B}}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Table 6 is illustrating this relationship from another point of view.

Table 6. A_t excludes B_t and vice versa.

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	+0	$p(b_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

The Sheffer Stroke

The Sheffer stroke notation, introduced by Henry Maurice Sheffer in 1913, represents a fundamental method in propositional logic. The Sheffer stroke, usually denoted by the symbol $\uparrow$, is a binary operation commonly referred to as “NAND”. This operation is significant as it can be interpreted as a form of negation of the logical “AND”. In formal logic, the Sheffer stroke is used to simplify logical expressions and to express various logical operations using only this single operation. In probability theory, the Sheffer stroke can be interpreted in a probabilistic context. Based on the 1913 Henry Maurice Sheffer (1882-1964) relationship, the Sheffer stroke (Sheffer, 1913; Nicod, 1917) usually denoted by $\uparrow$, is given by:

$$p(A_t | B_t) \equiv p(A_t \uparrow B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \wedge B_t) \tag{2}$$

¹Barukčić, Ilija. (2021). Mutually exclusive events. *Causation*, 16(11), 5–57. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5746415>

This equation shows the connection between the joint probability of two events A_t and B_t and the probability $p(A_t | B_t)$. The equation illustrates that the probability of the joint non-occurrence of two events is equal to 1 minus the probability of the joint co-occurrence of two events A_t and B_t at the same (period of) time t . This is a significant concept that finds application not only in logic but also in probability theory. Table 6 provides a detailed overview illustrating this relationship. The ability to simplify complex logical and probabilistic relationships using the Sheffer stroke operation has far-reaching implications. This consideration opens up interesting philosophical questions about the nature of probability and how we model natural processes mathematically. An alternative and equally valid formulation of an exclusion relationship is conceivable. Logical disjunction, denoted by $\vee$, is known for its commutative property. This means that the sequence in which operands are presented does not affect the result. Formally, this commutativity property of logical disjunction can be expressed as:

$$\neg A_t \vee \neg B_t \equiv \neg B_t \vee \neg A_t \quad (3)$$

For any events A_t and B_t at the same time t , the result of the disjunction remains unchanged regardless of the order of the operands. This characteristic is a fundamental aspect of logical disjunction. In other words, if A_t excludes B_t , then the converse is also true: B_t excludes A_t . In other words, if we have confidently identified someone as a man, we can be certain that he cannot be pregnant. Being a man inherently excludes the possibility of pregnancy, and the reverse is also true. If we identify a human being as pregnant, we know with certainty that this person cannot be a man. Pregnancy inherently excludes the possibility of being a man. Aristotle's **Principle of Excluded Middle** states that for any event A_t , either A_t is true or $\neg A_t$ (the negation of A_t) is true. In other words, there is no third between something and its own negation. Formally, from the point of view of a co-moving observer, this principle can be expressed as:

$$A_t \vee \neg A_t = \neg A_t \vee A_t = 1 - (A_t \wedge \neg A_t) = 1 \quad (4)$$

where $\wedge$ denotes logical conjunction (AND), $\vee$ denotes logical disjunction (OR), and $\neg$ denotes logical negation (NOT). The **Principle of Excluded Middle** and **Sheffer's Stroke** represent different aspects of objective reality. Both concepts are crucial for understanding objective reality effectively but are not identical.

However, are mathematical truths and principles discovered as inherent aspects of nature, or are they constructed by the human mind and then interpreted into nature or both or none et cetera? The **Principle of Excluded Middle** is not universally accepted in all logical systems. For example, intuitionistic (see [Brouwer, 1908](#); [Heyting, 1930](#)) or constructive logic is rejecting the **Principle of Excluded Middle** because it allows for the possibility of statements that are neither provably true nor provably false, which contrasts with the constructive approach to truth. Nonetheless, this principle has significant implications in mathematics, particularly in proofs by contradiction, where assuming that the negation of a statement leads to a contradiction, thus proving the original statement. Despite its foundational role in classical logic, the Principle of Excluded Middle continues to be a topic of philosophical debate, especially in discussions about the nature of truth and the limits of formal logic.

Example. Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) infection has afflicted millions of people worldwide, leading to a global pandemic 2019. Safe and effective vaccines have been developed to prevent laboratory-confirmed coronavirus disease 2019 (Covid-19). Polack² et al. (see Polack et al., 2020) conducted a multinational, placebo-controlled, observer-blinded, pivotal efficacy trial in a 1:1 ratio. Individuals aged 16 years or older received either two doses of placebo (n=21,728) or 30 μ g per dose of the lipid nanoparticle-formulated, nucleoside-modified RNA vaccine BNT162b2 (n=21,720), administered 21 days apart. There were 8 cases of Covid-19 in the vaccine group. The following table (see table 7) provides us with a suitable overview.

Table 7. BNT162b and COVID-19 (Study Polack et al., 2020).

		COVID-19		
		YES	NO	
BNT162b vaccine	YES	8	21712	21720
	NO	162	21566	21728
		170	43278	43448

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship k = -0,0567641832
p (EXCL) = 0,9998158718
p (EXCL) approx.= 0,9529411765
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— A_i) = 0,0029
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (EXCL— B_i) = 0,3765
p Value (EXCL) = 0,0001841112

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (nc) = 0,0494
RR (sc) = 0,0938
Vaccine efficacy (%) = 95,0599

ADDITIONAL MEASURES.

OR = 0,4965
IOR = -0,9059

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,496179341
p(IOI)= 0,495995213

The exclusion relationship is calculated in detail as follows.
 $p(\text{Vaccine} : \text{BNT162b2} \mid \text{COVID} - 19(\text{infection})) \equiv p(b_i) + p(c_i) + p(d_i) \equiv 1 - p(a_i) \equiv 1 - \left(\frac{8}{43538}\right) \equiv +0,99981625$, with a P Value = 0,000184.

²Polack FP, Thomas SJ, Kitchin N, Absalon J, Gurtman A, Lockhart S, Perez JL, Pérez Marc G, Moreira ED, Zerbini C, Bailey R, Swanson KA, Roychoudhury S, Koury K, Li P, Kalina WV, Cooper D, Frenck RW Jr, Hammitt LL, Türeci Ö, Nell H, Schaefer A, Ünal S, Tresnan DB, Mather S, Dormitzer PR, Şahin U, Jansen KU, Gruber WC; C4591001 Clinical Trial Group. Safety and Efficacy of the BNT162b2 mRNA Covid-19 Vaccine. *N Engl J Med.* 2020 Dec 31;383(27):2603-2615. doi: 10.1056/NEJMoa2034577. Epub 2020 Dec 10. PMID: 33301246; PMCID: PMC7745181.

Recommended P Value Thresholds

The P Value is a statistical measure that indicates the probability of obtaining results at least as extreme as those observed, assuming that the null hypothesis is true. A lower P Value suggests that the observed data is less likely under the null hypothesis, which can lead to rejecting the null hypothesis. In hypothesis testing, a P Value below a predefined threshold, such as 0.05, indicates strong evidence against the null hypothesis, suggesting that the observed effect is statistically significant. Polack et al. demonstrated with very high certainty that a two-dose regimen of BNT162b2 is highly effective in protecting against Covid-19 in individuals aged 16 years and older, with a p-value of 0.0001841112. We will examine this finding more closely. Since then, the ongoing pandemic has provided strong evidence that the nucleoside-modified RNA vaccine BNT162b2 offers excellent protection against Covid-19. Based on these and other findings, we should aim for a similar P Value in other studies as a benchmark to assess whether a drug or intervention is genuinely effective. Our experience with the study by Polack et al. and other similar studies indicates that we can establish more rigorous thresholds for statistical significance to draw reliable conclusions. Therefore, based on the insights gained from the study by Polack et al. and other similar research, the following P Value thresholds are advisable in order to be able to speak of well-established research findings:

1. For two-tailed questions, it is advisable to require a **P Value = 0.0002** or better.
2. For one-tailed questions, a **P Value = 0.0001** or better should be demanded.

Otherwise, although a relationship might seem plausible and possible, the same is not necessarily conclusively established beyond all doubt.

Fisher's exact test

Fisher's exact test is a statistical significance test which enable us to calculate the significance of the deviation from a null hypothesis (e.g., P Value) exactly. It is common practice to use Fisher's exact test (Fisher, 1935) often when the sample is very small but Fisher's exact test is valid for all sample sizes.

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(X \leq a) &= \sum_{i=0}^a \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \\
 &= \sum_{i=0}^8 \frac{\binom{21720}{i} \binom{43448-21720}{170-i}}{\binom{43448}{170}} \\
 &= \frac{6.7686358877995}{100\,000\,000\,000\,000\,000\,000} \\
 &= 6.7686358877995e - 20 \\
 &= \text{P Value (one sided left tailed)}
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Following Kolmogorov's definition of an n-dimensional probability density (see also [Kolmogorov, Andreĭ Nikolaevich, 1950](#), p. 26) of random variables A_t , B_t et cetera at the point t , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t | B_t) &\equiv p(\underline{A}_t \cup \underline{B}_t) \\
 &\equiv 1 - p(A_t \cap B_t) \\
 &\equiv 1 - \int_{-\infty}^{A_t} \int_{-\infty}^{B_t} f(A_t, B_t) dA_t dB_t \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

while $p(A_t | B_t)$ would denote the cumulative distribution function of random variables and $f(A_t, B_t)$ is the joint density function.

2.2.1. Observational study and exclusion relationship

Under conditions of an observational study, the exclusion relationship follows approximately (see [Barukčić, 2021](#)) as

$$p(A_t | B_t) \equiv p(A_t \uparrow B_t) \geq 1 - \frac{p(a_t)}{p(B_t)} \tag{7}$$

2.2.2. Experimental study and exclusion relationship

Under conditions of an experimental study, the exclusion relationship follows approximately (see [Barukčić, 2021](#)) as

$$p(A_t | B_t) \equiv p(A_t \uparrow B_t) \geq 1 - \frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)} \tag{8}$$

2.2.3. The goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship

DEFINITION 2 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, testing hypothesis about an exclusion relationship $p(A_t | B_t)$ is possible by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | A) &\equiv \frac{(b - (a + b))^2}{A} + \frac{((c + d) - \underline{A})^2}{\underline{A}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{A} + 0 \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{A}
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | B) &\equiv \frac{(c - (a + c))^2}{B} + \frac{((b + d) - \underline{B})^2}{\underline{B}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{B} + 0 \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{B}
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution equals zero when the observed values are equal to the expected/theoretical values of an exclusion relationship/distribution $p(A_t | B_t)$, in which case the null hypothesis has to be accepted. Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction was not used under these circumstances.

2.2.4. The left-tailed p Value of an exclusion relationship

DEFINITION 3 (The left-tailed p Value of an exclusion relationship).

It is known that as a sample size, N , increases, a sampling distribution of a special test statistic approaches the normal distribution (central limit theorem). Under these circumstances, the left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019) of an exclusion relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 pValue_{lt}(A_t | B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t|B_t))} \\
 &\equiv 1 - e^{-(a/N)}
 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

A low p-value may provide some evidence of statistical significance.

3. Results

CLEAR Outcomes trial

Nissen et al. (see [Nissen et al., 2023](#)) published data of a multi-year, double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled trial with a median follow-up duration of 40.6 months (approximately 3.4 years) involving 13970 patients who were unable or unwilling to take statins.

Table 8. Relationship: Bempedoic acid and death from any cause (Study of Nissen et al. , 2023).

		Death from any cause		
		YES	NO	
Bempedoic acid	YES	434	6558	6992
	NO	420	6558	6978
		854	13116	13970

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = +0,00392739$
 P Value (one sided left tailed) (Fisher's exact test) = 0,69127659
 p (EXCL) = 0,96893343
 p (EXCL) approx.= $1-(a/A) >$ 0,93792906
 p (EXCL) approx.= $1-(a/B) >$ 0,49180328

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,69127659
 χ^2 (EXCL— A_i) = 26,93878719
 χ^2 (EXCL— B_i) = 220,55737705
 P Value (EXCL) = 0,03058896

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/N) \times 100 = (434 / 13970) \times 100 = 3,11 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (6558 / 13970) \times 100 = 46,94 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (420 / 13970) \times 100 = 3,01 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (6558 / 13970) \times 100 = 46,94 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (434 / 6992) \times 100 = 6,21 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (6558 / 6992) \times 100 = 93,79 \%$
 $(c/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (420 / 6978) \times 100 = 6,02 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (6558 / 6978) \times 100 = 93,98 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (434 / 854) \times 100 = 50,82 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (420 / 854) \times 100 = 49,18 \%$
 $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (6558 / 13116) \times 100 = 50,00 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (6558 / 13116) \times 100 = 50,00 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (6992 / 13970) \times 100 = 50,05 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (6978 / 13970) \times 100 = 49,95 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (854 / 13970) \times 100 = 6,11 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (13116 / 13970) \times 100 = 93,89 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 1,03126430
 RR (sufficient condition) = 1,01639344

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 1,03333333
 Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,01537589

STUDY DESIGN.

$p(\text{IOU}) = 0,43836793$
 $p(\text{IOI}) = 0,43937008$

The *CLEAR Outcomes* trial (see [Nissen et al., 2023](#)) provided robust evidence that LDL cholesterol was significantly reduced by administering bempedoic acid.

“The mean LDL cholesterol level at baseline was 139.0 mg per deciliter in both groups, and after 6 months, the reduction in the level was greater with bempedoic acid than with placebo by 29.2 mg per deciliter; the observed difference in the percent reductions was 21.1 percentage points in favor of bempedoic acid.” (see [Nissen et al., 2023](#))

However, at the same time, this reduction in LDL levels did not correspond with a decrease in death from any cause (causal relationship $k > 0$; relative risk > 1 ; IOR > 0) or at least with a decrease in cardiovascular death (causal relationship $k > 0$; relative risk > 1 ; IOR > 0). In other words, bempedoic acid does not exclude death from any cause.

Unfortunately, there is an indication—albeit not definitively significant—that bempedoic acid might have contributed causally to overall mortality (causal relationship $k > 0$; relative risk > 1 ; IOR > 0). The death from any cause occurred in 434 out of 6992 patients (6.2%) in the bempedoic acid group, compared to 420 out of 6978 patients (6.0%) in the placebo group. We cannot exclude that the slight difference of $6.2\% - 6.0\% = 0.2\%$, or approximately $2 \times 6992/1000 = 14$ additional deaths, is causally linked to the intake of bempedoic acid (causal relationship $k > 0$; relative risk > 1 ; IOR > 0).

Nonetheless, there is not really a robust or conclusive evidence that the slight difference of $6.2\% - 6.0\% = 0.2\%$ additional deaths is causally linked to the intake of bempedoic acid. If the medication with bempedoic acid itself contributed to increased mortality, a noticeably higher death rate, then the observed $\frac{434}{6992}$ deaths in the treatment group would be expected. Yet, the published data does not support such a hypothesis beyond any doubt. In other words, it is difficult to causally attribute part of the observed $\frac{434}{6992}$ deaths to the intake of bempedoic acid itself.

No matter how hard one may try, it is impossible to overlook that a significant reduction in LDL achieved in the 13970 patients *CLEAR Outcomes* trial (see [Nissen et al., 2023](#)) did not result in a parallel decrease of death from any cause. The alarming implications of the data from the *CLEAR Outcomes* trial **either** profoundly challenge the established causal role of LDL in the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis **or** raise serious questions about the safety of the bempedoic acid medication, warranting urgent and thorough reevaluation.

CLEAR Outcomes trial with fictive data (unfair study design)

Nissen et al. (see [Nissen et al., 2023](#)) conducted a 13970 patients *CLEAR Outcomes* double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled trial involving patients who were unable or unwilling to take statins. The following study is based on fictional data (in the treatment group). We assume that bempedoic acid is indeed effective in reducing cardiovascular mortality. In this scenario, we expect 30% fewer deaths in the verum group calculated as follows:

$$(420 \times (1 - 0.30)) \times \frac{6992}{6978} = 294.18 \approx 294 \text{ expected deaths in the treatment group.}$$

The table 9 presents this relationship in tabular form.

Table 9. Relationship: Bempedoic acid and death from any cause (Study of Nissen et al. , 2023).

		Death from any cause		
		YES	NO	
Bempedoic acid	YES	294	6698	6992
	NO	420	6558	6978
		714	13256	13970

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = -0,04118838$
 P Value (one sided left tailed) (Fisher's exact test) = 0,00000065
p (EXCL) = 0,97895490
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,95795195
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,58823529

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000065
 χ^2 (EXCL— A₁) = 12,36212815
 χ^2 (EXCL— B₁) = 121,05882353
 P Value (EXCL) = **0,02082519**

PROPORTIONS.

(a/N) × 100 = (294 / 13970) × 100 = 2,10 %
 (b/N) × 100 = (6698 / 13970) × 100 = 47,95 %
 (c/N) × 100 = (420 / 13970) × 100 = 3,01 %
 (d/N) × 100 = (6558 / 13970) × 100 = 46,94 %
(a/A) × 100 = (294 / 6992) × 100 = 4,20 %
 (b/A) × 100 = (6698 / 6992) × 100 = 95,80 %
(c/ not A) × 100 = (420 / 6978) × 100 = 6,02 %
 (d/ not A) × 100 = (6558 / 6978) × 100 = 93,98 %
 (a/B) × 100 = (294 / 714) × 100 = 41,18 %
 (c/B) × 100 = (420 / 714) × 100 = 58,82 %
 (b/ not B) × 100 = (6698 / 13256) × 100 = 50,53 %
 (d/ not B) × 100 = (6558 / 13256) × 100 = 49,47 %
 (A/N) × 100 = (6992 / 13970) × 100 = 50,05 %
 (not A/N) × 100 = (6978 / 13970) × 100 = 49,95 %
 (B/N) × 100 = (714 / 13970) × 100 = 5,11 %
 (not B/N) × 100 = (13256 / 13970) × 100 = 94,89 %

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 0,69859840
 RR (sufficient condition) = 0,81492280

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 0,68536877
 Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,17729506

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,44838941
p(IOI)= 0,44939155

Under these conditions, Bempedoic acid were effective against cardiovascular death (causal relationship < 0; relative risk < 1; index of relationship < 0; P-Value (two-sided) = 0,02082519). However, this has not been the case.

CLEAR Outcomes trial with fictive data (fair study design)

Nissen et al. reported death from cardiovascular causes as 269/6992 (3.8 %, Bempedoic group) and 257/6978 (3.7 %, placebo group). Table 10 provides an overview.

Table 10. Relationship: Bempedoic acid and cardiovascular death (Study of Nissen et al. , 2023).

		Cardiovascular death		
		YES	NO	
Bempedoic acid	YES	269	6723	6992
	NO	257	6721	6978
		526	13444	13970

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,00431435$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (Fisher's exact test) = 0,71031805
 p (EXCL) = 0,98074445
 p (EXCL) approx.= $1-(a/A) > 0,96152746$
 p (EXCL) approx.= $1-(a/B) > 0,48859316$

P VALUES.
P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,71031805
 χ^2 (EXCL— A_i) = 10,34911327
 χ^2 (EXCL— B_i) = 137,56844106
P Value (EXCL) = **0,01907134**

PROPORTIONS.
 $(a/N) \times 100 = (269 / 13970) \times 100 = 1,93 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (6723 / 13970) \times 100 = 48,12 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (257 / 13970) \times 100 = 1,84 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (6721 / 13970) \times 100 = 48,11 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (269 / 6992) \times 100 = 3,85 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (6723 / 6992) \times 100 = 96,15 \%$
 $(c/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (257 / 6978) \times 100 = 3,68 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } A) \times 100 = (6721 / 6978) \times 100 = 96,32 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (269 / 526) \times 100 = 51,14 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (257 / 526) \times 100 = 48,86 \%$
 $(b/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (6723 / 13444) \times 100 = 50,01 \%$
 $(d/ \text{not } B) \times 100 = (6721 / 13444) \times 100 = 49,99 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (6992 / 13970) \times 100 = 50,05 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (6978 / 13970) \times 100 = 49,95 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (526 / 13970) \times 100 = 3,77 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (13444 / 13970) \times 100 = 96,23 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).
RR (necessary condition) = 1,04459683
RR (sufficient condition) = 1,02266155

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.
Odds ratio (OR) = 1,04638123
Index of relationship (IOR) = 0,02178970

STUDY DESIGN.
 $p(\text{IOU}) = 0,46184681$
 $p(\text{IOI}) = 0,46284896$

The expected number of cardiovascular deaths in the treatment group can be calculated as follows:

$$\text{Expected deaths} = (257 \times (1 - 0.30)) \times \frac{6992}{6978} = 179.9 \times 1.002 \approx 180.3$$

In contrast to the expected 180 cardiovascular deaths, 269 cardiovascular deaths were observed in the bempedoic acid group, representing a substantial deviation:

$$\text{Percentage difference} = \frac{269 - 180}{180} \times 100 \approx +49.44\%$$

This observed difference suggests that bempedoic acid does not effectively reduce cardiovascular mortality (causal relationship > 0 ; relative risk > 1 ; index of relationship > 0 ; P -value = 0.0191). On the contrary, bempedoic acid appears to causally contribute to fatal cardiovascular mortality.

CLEAR Outcomes trial with fictive data

The following analysis is based on hypothetical data for the treatment group. These are the data that would have been expected if bempedoic acid were truly effective in preventing cardiovascular death (see Table 11).

Table 11. Relationship: Bempedoic acid and cardiovascular death, verum group: fictive data (Study of Nissen et al. , 2023).

		Cardiovascular death		
		YES	NO	
Bempedoic acid	YES	180	6812	6992
	NO	257	6721	6978
		437	13533	13970

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = -0,03184317$
P Value (one sided left tailed) (Fisher's exact test) = 0,00009824
p (EXCL) = 0,98711525
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/A) > 0,97425629
p (EXCL) approx.= 1-(a/B) > 0,58810069

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided left tailed) (HGD) = 0,00009824
 χ^2 (EXCL— A_i) = 4,63386728
 χ^2 (EXCL— B_i) = 74,14187643
P Value (EXCL) = **0,01280210**

PROPORTIONS.

(a/N) × 100 = (180 / 13970) × 100 = 1,29 %
(b/N) × 100 = (6812 / 13970) × 100 = 48,76 %
(c/N) × 100 = (257 / 13970) × 100 = 1,84 %
(d/N) × 100 = (6721 / 13970) × 100 = 48,11 %
(a/A) × 100 = (180 / 6992) × 100 = 2,57 %
(b/A) × 100 = (6812 / 6992) × 100 = 97,43 %
(c/ not A) × 100 = (257 / 6978) × 100 = 3,68 %
(d/ not A) × 100 = (6721 / 6978) × 100 = 96,32 %
(a/B) × 100 = (180 / 437) × 100 = 41,19 %
(c/B) × 100 = (257 / 437) × 100 = 58,81 %
(b/ not B) × 100 = (6812 / 13533) × 100 = 50,34 %
(d/ not B) × 100 = (6721 / 13533) × 100 = 49,66 %
(A/N) × 100 = (6992 / 13970) × 100 = 50,05 %
(not A/N) × 100 = (6978 / 13970) × 100 = 49,95 %
(B/N) × 100 = (437 / 13970) × 100 = 3,13 %
(not B/N) × 100 = (13533 / 13970) × 100 = 96,87 %

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 0,69898672
RR (sufficient condition) = 0,81829616

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 0,69103276
Index of relationship (IOR) = -0,17702611

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= 0,46821761
p(IOI)= 0,46921976

Under these circumstances, evidence would have been established that bempedoic acid is indeed effective in preventing cardiovascular death (causal relationship < 0; relative risk < 1; index of relationship < 0; P-Value (two-sided) = 0,01280210). As previously detailed, unfortunately, this was not the case.

4. Discussion

The *CLEAR Outcomes* trial has provided robust evidence that bempedoic acid significantly lowers LDL cholesterol levels with an acceptable side effect profile. With a sample size of $N = 13,970$ patients, this study and its findings cannot be easily dismissed.

However, it is particularly noteworthy that despite the effective and statistically significant reduction in LDL cholesterol achieved by bempedoic acid, there was no observed reduction in all-cause mortality. In the group receiving bempedoic acid, a mortality rate approximately 30% lower than that of the placebo group was anticipated. Yet, this outcome was not observed.

Given this fact, we are compelled to consider that reducing LDL cholesterol alone does not necessarily lead to lower cardiovascular mortality. Rather, it appears that the specific mechanism by which LDL is reduced plays a critical role. To date, this has predominantly been achieved through the use of statins.

Statins are able to efficiently inhibit cholesterol synthesis by blocking 3-hydroxy-3-methylglutaryl (HMG)-CoA reductase in the mevalonate pathway. However, the demonstrated cardiovascular mortality reduction (see [Horne et al., 2003](#)) attributed to statins is likely not solely a result of LDL reduction. Instead, it may stem from other effects of statins, including their noted anti-infective properties (see [Wu et al., 2022](#)). Statins, primarily known for their lipid-lowering effects, have been observed to exhibit significant anti-infective properties (see [Ponroy et al., 2015](#)), particularly against the cytomegalovirus (CMV). There is accumulated evidence that infectious agents such as cytomegalovirus (CMV) are related to atherosclerotic disease (see [Parrinello et al., 2012](#)). Subjects in the highest CMV IgG group have increased all-cause mortality relative to CMV-seronegatives (see [Chen et al., 2021](#)).

CMV, a member of the herpesvirus family (see [Whitley, 1996](#)), can cause serious infections, especially in immunocompromised individuals. Studies suggest that statins can inhibit CMV replication by interfering with the viral life cycle. They achieve this through multiple mechanisms, including the modulation of host cell signaling pathways and the reduction of pro-inflammatory cytokine production, which can otherwise facilitate viral propagation.

Research indicates that statins (see [Mohd Jaafar et al., 2021](#)) may impair the expression of viral genes by affecting the host's mevalonate pathway (see [Warita et al., 2014](#)), which is crucial for viral replication. Additionally, statins have been shown to enhance the antiviral immune response, promoting the activation of T-cells that target CMV-infected cells. This dual action of direct antiviral effects and immune modulation may contribute to the observed reduction in CMV-related complications among patients receiving statins.

Moreover, clinical studies have reported a relationship between statin use and decreased rates of CMV reactivation in organ transplant recipients, underscoring their potential protective role. Such findings highlight the importance of considering statins not only for their cardiovascular benefits but also for their potential utility in managing viral infections like CMV. This broader perspective could

lead to more comprehensive treatment strategies for patients at risk for both cardiovascular diseases and viral infections.

5. Conclusion

Based on the previous presentations, we have no alternative but to reach the following preliminary conclusion.

The *CLEAR Outcomes* trial casts substantial doubt on the “LDL hypothesis” of atherosclerosis, providing valuable insights in this context. For now, based on the data of the *CLEAR Outcomes* trial, we cannot conclude that within LDL the definitive cause of atherosclerosis will be found.

Acknowledgments

No funding or any financial support by a third party was received.

Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections’ introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are frequently used:

CMV	Cytomegalovirus
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
EBV	Epstein-Bar virus
IHC	Immunohistochemistry
ISH	In situ hybridization
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction
BMI	body mass index
ESRD	end-stage renal disease
HD	hemodialysis
CABG	coronary artery bypass graft
CCI	Charlson comorbidity index
AMI	acute myocardial infarction
MACE	major adverse cardiovascular events
LDL-C	low-density lipoprotein cholesterol
GFR	glomerular filtration rate
STEMI	ST elevation myocardial infarction
NSTEMI	non-ST elevation myocardial infarction
MI	myocardial infarction
ARB	angiotensin receptor blocker
ACEI	angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors
CCBs	calcium channel blockers
IOR	index of relationship
p(IOU)	index of unfairness
p(IOI)	index of independence
k	Causal relationship
SINE	Necessary condition relationship
IMP	Sufficient condition relationship
EXCL	exclusion relationship
RR	Relative risk
RR (nc)	relative risk (necessary condition)
RR (sc)	relative risk (sufficient condition)
OR	Odds ratio
P Value	Probability of significance

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Associated Data

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality.**

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